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International interaction and global peace in light of international convergence: a strategy to achieve environmental diplomacy

Abstract:

Nowadays, two fundamental pillars of human existence are environmental protection and sustainable development. Governments and international organizations play an important role in this process. Without serious regional interactions and international cooperation, sustainability in development and environmental protection will not happen. Except for international interactions and global peace, sustainable development and development sustainability are not on their accurate paths. An effective method for natural resources and ecosystems conservation is environmental diplomacy. Therefore, environmental discussions are extremely important reasons for international convergence. Through convergence attitude, the international community can reach the global environmental conservation strategies. In this study, it is attempted to determine the international environmental law evolution and the governments' roles in environmental challenges underlying the international convergence and legal fundamentals. It is concluded that, environmental threats and hazards resulted from illogical human act can be solved by international convergence, environmental conservation and global peace.

Keywords: Convergence, Global peace, International environmental diplomacy, International environmental law, International interactions and collaborations Sobhan Tayebi Contact Info:

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